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**AND VIEWS OF SCIENTISTS IN THE FORMATION OF THE
INDEPENDENCE OF KNOWLEDGE****Khojiev Azizjon Kaimovich**

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Today's in the day of students' knowledge to get and independent thought exchange development about collection pedagogue our scientists scientific studies and research take is going In students' knowledge independence development to history look that puts if we education and education in the process one series foreign scientists are also young generation knowledge take more improve in order to work came out methodical and Methodical manuals example we bring can For example The work of the Swiss pedagogue-democrat IG Pestalossi plays an important role in the development of teaching methods that help students develop their independence of knowledge. The scientist considers that the main goal of teaching is to stimulate the minds of students to active activities, to develop their cognitive abilities, and to develop the ability to think independently. He wrote: "My students do not learn new things from me; they discover these new things on their own. My main task is to help them open up and develop their ideas" [1].

In the XVIII-XIX centuries. the development of pedagogy is associated with the emergence of the doctrine of utopian socialism. A. Saint-Simon, Sh. Fure, R. Owen put forward large-scale, genius projects of pedagogical reforms, in which the idea of educating an "independent and rational thinking person" is given a great place. For example, R. Owen in his book "On the Education of Human Character" developed the idea of the importance of combining the education of children with physical, aesthetic education, and the development of practical skills, which leads to their cognitive independence. , shows that it helps to improve the human personality.

BGANanev, analyzing the formation process of human character. says that reflexive properties are formed much later than other qualities of a person. According to him: "a person passes through many objects of mutual relations during his life, as a result of which his consciousness becomes an object of self-awareness. It is necessary to accumulate the experience of awareness many times as a subject of his behavior and to turn his attitude towards it into a character, which we call reflection. This idea gives an opportunity to conclude

about the need to create certain conditions and situations that ensure the development of professional reflection and, as a result, the formation of reflexive aspects determined by the characteristics of a person's activity.

The famous pedagogue-democrat A. Disterweg put the principle of independence of students in education in the first place in his didactic views, and he played a major role in the fight against educational dogmatism in Germany at the beginning of the 19th century. He believes that it is the duty of man to take the initiative in the pursuit of rational goals. Therefore, in his opinion, the teacher should create the tendency of students to know. A. Disterweg distinguishes two methods of teaching: informative and developmental. In the first, dogmatic acquisition of knowledge takes place. In the second, it creates the initiative of students, the activity of their own thoughts. Also, the scientist divides the developing method into developing-questioning (heuristic conversation) and developing-explanatory (teacher's story) types. In the developmental education method, "thinking, and as a result, questions and answers, searching and finding the truth take flight" [2, p. 182].

In the industrialized countries of Europe and America at the beginning of the 20th century, the goals of education were determined by the tasks of increasing productivity in general. Therefore, education was mainly pragmatic in nature. In a number of Western countries, *pragmatic pedagogy formed the* theoretical basis of the education and training process , which set the task of educating an independent person who can adapt to life, giving him relevant life knowledge, skills and abilities . In this regard, the works of representatives of this direction (D.J. Dewey, W. Kilpatrick, H. Parkhurst, etc.) are of particular interest.

We will dwell on the main philosophical and pedagogical principles of J. Dewey's teaching related to the problem of independence of knowledge. These include the following rules:

Figure 1: Knowledge related to the problem of independence the rules scheme

Another representative of pragmatic pedagogy, U. Kilpatrick [3] describes the method of projects, according to which students' independence is formed in the process of choosing and designing their activities, and knowledge is formed through them. The material for learning is taken from everyday life. The students themselves chose what the content of the study would be, that is, the teacher only helped them to implement their plans.

In the same way, the problem of educating cognitive independence was solved according to the "Dalton Plan" developed by Helen Parkhurst in the early 20th century. Traditional activities in the form of lessons have been canceled. Students received written assignments and worked on them independently based on an individual plan after consulting with teachers. A similar system (appropriately adapted) is now used in many European universities.

Modern approaches to the formation of cognitive independence are inextricably linked with the names of the creators of the concept of humanistic education and personality development, which appeared in the 60s and 80s of the 20th century [4]. The basis of this concept was provided by Gordon Allport ("Dispositional Theory of Personality"), Abraham Maslow ("Humanistic Theory of Personality"), Carl Rogers ("Phenomenological Theory of Personality") and others. organizes work. In this, the authors of humanistic theories of personality are based on the existentialist principle of self-awareness of the individual. For example, A. Maslow states that the purpose of education is ultimately the manifestation of

the individual [5]. K. Rodgers [6] to initiative, self-regulation and self-awareness suggests building based education. The advantages of such teaching are the student's conscious, responsible and ultimately independent participation in education, his willingness to always be open to the perception of new experiences and to constantly change himself as the surrounding reality changes.

This thesis through From the point of view of the problem of the independence of knowledge, the humanistic direction based on the existentialist theory focuses on learning in personal experience based on initiative, self-regulation and self-awareness. According to the humanistic concept, learning experience helps a person to identify his personal characteristics that distinguish him from others, to discover thoughts, actions and experiences that have a universal character. In this concept, teaching is essentially equated with the process of personality formation, and independence of knowledge becomes its main quality. It is this that constitutes the social aspect of the problem of independence of knowledge.

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